

TRANSVERSE WAVE RECT ZONE BASED DYNAMIC ADAPTIVE SECURE ROUTING FOR MOBILE AD HOC AND SENSOR NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

A Mobile Ad-Hoc Sensor Networks (MASNET) is a collection of wireless mobile nodes without any pre-defined topology and infrastructure. This does not rely on any centralized access point, or administration. Due to this nature and characteristics it affected by severe network overhead and energy based issues. To decreased routing overhead, and to achieve higher packet delivery ratio MASNET, there are several routing protocols are designed and developed in the literature. In specific, the location aided routing protocols have tremendous growth and usage in this networks. So, in this paper, we proposed a new transverse wave zone based secure location aided routing scheme named as TWRect with Dynamic Adaptive Secure Routing which utilizes the node location information with wave zone selection, and make forwarding decision based on that. This will greatly reduce the flooding control packet count and decreases search zone. Finally, this will results in low routing overhead in the network with improved security. With the help of node mobility analysis, the zone selection, and route discovery process is reused. The simulation results show the impact of TWrect zone improves the efficiency in energy minimization, and data delivery.

KEYWORDS

MASNET, Ad-Hoc Network, Sensor Network, Location Aided Routing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mobile Ad hoc sensor networks (MASNET) are the types of Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANETs), which are considered with energy and resource [1]. MASNETs are temporary self-configuring and multi-hop networks of wireless mobile and sensor nodes that dynamically establish their networks when required, without relying on any pre-existing infrastructure or predefined network topology. Since Wireless sensor network

have severe resource constraints due to their lack of processing power, limited memory, and bandwidth. Consequently, they have the characteristics, requirements, and limitations of both MANETs and WSNs. These networks have enabled a wide variety of applications such as Environmental monitoring, medical monitoring, and control of industrial processes including agriculture, and smart homes or smart cities [2]. In these applications, mobility is the major issue, and it poses many network performances issues. Provide a high performance, and secure routing algorithm that is capable of dynamically changing its topology in the mobile environment with minimal consumption of a energy is more challenging part. In MASNETs, the main reason for the topology change is because of the mobility of mobile nodes. And fin few scenarios, the node may get failure due to energy exhaustion. Since these sensors nodes are limited in power supply and have low radio frequency coverage and this can easily lose their connection with neighbors. These will create new difficulties in updating their routing tables.

Many researchers have proposed many routing protocols for MASNETs [3]. But, those protocols severely undergo many issues such as route maintenance overhead and transmission overhead. Route maintenance mechanisms need more controls Packets (CP), which need to be transmitted whenever there is a transformation in the network topology structure. Transmitting of such control packets consume more energies and bandwidth usage. This creates high failure rate among mobile nodes in the network. This paper provides a new approach to handle the location aided routing in more effective manner.

A. Overview of MASNETs:

The concept of MASNETs has emerged in recent years because more complex applications require sensor nodes to be mobile rather than static, such as in smart transport systems, security systems and social interaction [4]. In such applications, the mobile sensor nodes are able to sense, compute, and communicate like immobile or less mobility sensor nodes. However, mobile nodes are able to cooperatively interact, reposition and organize itself in the network. MASNETs can start with some initial deployment and nodes can then spread out together information. Information gathered by a mobile node can be communicated to another mobile node when they are within range of each other. In this section, MASNETs are reviewed regarding their characteristics, current applications and research challenges.

B. Characteristics of MASNETs:

Most of the major characteristics of MASNETs are the same as that of normal static sensor networks. However, there are some major differences that distinguish MASNETs from other networks which can be described regarding different aspects such as accurate localization of nodes, Recurrent Topology Transform, recurrent topology

transformation, excessive energy utilization, communication space minimization between nodes, better reliability and targeting nodes, and so on [5].

Accurate localization: The estimation of position and location of sensor nodes are very important in mobile environment. Thus, it is very critical to have an accurate knowledge of the location of the sink or node for packet transmission. The mobile sink can sense and collect more data from wider area due to the mobility of the sink.

Recurrent Topology Transformation: Due to their mobility, MASNETs have a much more frequent topology change compared to the static adhoc sensor networks. This change in topology of MASNETs makes data become outdated speedily. So, a new dynamic routing protocol is needed in such mobile environment.

Excessive energy utilization: The mobile sensor nodes in MASNETs require additional energy to perform the high mobility compared to immobile or less mobility sensor nodes. The frequent topology change due to mobility also consumes energy for establish communication.

Communication space minimization: The mobile nodes can be relocated after the initial deployment to reduce the communication gap between different nodes in the network. The static nodes can only use the default transmission range to communicate with their neighbouring nodes.

Better data reliability and targeting: The mobility of nodes can reduce the number of hops, and then decrease the probability of errors during transmission. As mobile sensor nodes are generally deployed randomly instead of precisely, nodes are required to move for a better sight or closer proximity. With the advantages of mobile nodes in MASNETs, various potential applications of MASNETs can be deployed in a real world. Since MASNETs are new type of networks, its specific unique applications areas are yet to be clearly defined. Most of their application scenarios are the same as that of static sensor networks. The only difference is the mobility of sink or sensor nodes existed in different applications of MASNETs.

Dynamic routing protocols: The increased mobility in the case of MASNETs imposes some restrictions on the existing routing protocols [6,7,8] for sensor networks. Most of the efficient protocols in the static sensor networks perform poorly in mobile environment. Thus, the efficient dynamic routing protocols are needed for MASNETs. Most of the aspects described show the effects of mobility on the mobile nodes in MASNETs. However, there are some advantages of mobile nodes that make them better than the static nodes such as dynamic data collection and location based data service acquisition.

Communication link imperfection:Due to the frequent topology change of MASNETs, the links for communication between different nodes often become unstable and unreliable, especially in hostile Environments and remote areas. The failure in packet transmission due to broken links requires further research on QoS of MASNETs.

Network Restructure:The mobile nodes can be used to reorganize the network with a proper setting of mobility model. The static nodes can only turn into disconnected sub-network due to energy depletion or hardware failure.

Efficient energy utilization:The mobile nodes can be used to reduce energy consumption during communication in the network by reducing the gap between different nodes when they are relocated near to sink. The base stations or sensor nodes can also move and the energy dissipation is more efficient. The static nodes near the gateway will die sooner due to the many-to-one hop-by-hop communication pattern.

C. Energy Consumption in MASNETs:

MASNETs typically consist of a number of joint mobile and immobile or less mobility mobile/sensor nodes, which capable of performing many processing, data collection, data transformation, node localization and communicating with other connected nodes in the network. Usually, these sensors nodes are energy constrained and operated in high dynamic network areas. Therefore, they must sustain their energy source as long as possible [9]. However, there are several facets put a restriction to their energy sources. This includes ineffective routing, recurrent route updating and request packet flooding. So there is a necessity to reduce the energy in MASNET by adopting location aided routing protocols with additional features. There are several ways to reduce the energy in MASNET. The following are the some techniques for efficient routing with less energy consumption.

Energy efficient methods and routing protocols:

With the energy-constrained nature of wireless networks, it is very important to use energy efficient techniques in the design of routing protocol to maximize the network lifetime of MASNETs. These techniques can be classified as follows:

Node activity scheduling:The main idea of this method is scheduling node activity is to alternate node states between sleeping and active to minimize energy consumption while ensuring the network and application functionalities. This idea reduces the energy consumption in MASNET.

Location aided Routing: location aided routing process is the process of utilizing location information, and it reduces the search zone, and number of routing messages. This also includes the speed, and direction information of a mobile node which more minimizes the search zone and increases the probability of the node finding [10].

Reducing the volume of information transferred: These strategies is aggregating information with the use of clusters and to those clusters the data will be disseminated.

Energy efficient routing: The goal of this technique is to minimize the energy consumed by the end-to-end transmission of a packet to avoid nodes with a low residual energy and reduce the number of unsuccessful transmissions.

Most of them aim to minimize the energy consumption in communication. These routings protocols can be classified based on their network structure, state of information, energy efficiency techniques and mobility as classified]. Such energy-aware routing protocols and techniques also need to be addressed for collective groups of communicating sensor nodes to have better overall performance and improved energy efficiency in the entire MASNets. In location aided routing, each node knows its current location and by using the last known location information and average speed the route discovery process will begin. It defined by two terminologies such as expected zone and request zone. The expected zone is limited to the destination zone and the request zone restricts the packet flooding. In this case, the route discovery is imitated when the source does not aware a route to its destination and the previous link is broken.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Design of routing protocols for MASNets is a crucial problem due to its different unique characters. To provide better routing regarding security and reliability many routing algorithms have been developed in the literature. To reduce the energy and resource in MASNets, Location Aided Routing (LAR) protocols are introduced. This paper surveys various recent and effective techniques and methods used for energy efficient location aided routing in MASNets. The LAR protocols reduce the search for a new route to a lesser request zone of the ad hoc network. This gradually reduces the overhead due to the larger zone route request. Many common MANET routing algorithms do not take into account the physical location of a destination node.

Shih, Tzay-Farn (2008)[11], authors proposed a location-based routing protocol called LARDAR. There are three important characteristics being used in the protocol to improve the performance. Initially authors used the location information of the destination node to predict a smaller triangle or rectangle request zone. This predicted based on the coverage of the destination position in the past. The smaller route discovery space reduces the traffic of route request and the probability of collision. The next process is to estimate request zone to reduce the searching range and achieved high precision. Authors then

applied a dynamic adaptation of request zone technique which helps to activate intermediate nodes. This utilizes the location information of destination node. These helps to redefine a more precise request zone in the network. In conclusion, an increasing exclusive search approach is developed to rebuild route discovery by a progressive increasing search angle basis. This will be done when the route discovery unsuccessful. It is helpful to reduce routing overhead in the network. It guarantees that the areas of route rediscovery will never exceed twice the entire network. The LARDAR has lower routing cost and collision than other protocols.

Wang et al. (2009)[12] have proposed an efficient greedy location aided routing protocol (GLAR) for energy effective routing. This improves the efficiency of location aided routing protocol in MANETs. Here authors formulated a decision on a baseline, which is line in between source node and the destination node. This baseline is used to broadcast the request packets in request zone for route discovery. The node with the shortest distance to baseline is selected as a next hope during broadcast. Here authors compared GLAR with basic LAR, and result shows that proposed GLAR can reduce the network overhead and increase network lifetime.

Lee, Yoo and Kim (2010) [13] proposed a mechanism that considers not only the location of nodes but energy consumption to solve the several problems in wireless networks by improving LAR algorithm. This protocol gives efficient routing by reducing the flooding of unnecessary control packets in the network. This also considers the limited energy of a mobile node and using appropriate transfer power to communicate portal. The improving LAR scheme can reduce energy consumption, and the average lifetime increases 12% than Location Aided Routing Protocol.

Xiao Hui Li et al. (2011) [14] have proposed a Location-Based Self Adaptive Routing Algorithm for Wireless Sensor Networks in Home Automation (WSNHA-LBAR). This proposed protocol use cylindrical request zone, hence during route discovery phase, restricted flooding reduces the routing control overhead, and decreases broadcast storm problems. Also, by using a self adaptive algorithm based on Bayes theorem, WSNHA-LBAR automatically adjusts the size of the request zone. WSNHALBAR uses the location information of the sensor nodes to restrict the flooding route searching space to a smaller estimated request zone, which represents the route-searched zone. By simulation authors show that WSNHA-LBAR improved network reliability, and also reduced routing overhead in network while compare with AODVjr routing protocol.

Haidar Safa, Hassan Artail and Diana Tabet (2012) [15] propose a novel cluster based trust-aware routing protocol (CBTRP) for MANETs to protect forwarded packets from intermediary malicious nodes. The proposed protocol organizes the network into one-hop disjoint clusters then elect the most qualified and trustworthy nodes to play the role of cluster-heads that are responsible for handling all the routing activities. The proposed

CBTRP continuously ensures the trustworthiness of cluster-heads by replacing them as soon as they become malicious and can dynamically update the packet path to avoid malicious routes.

PutthiphongKirdpipat and Sakchai Thipchaksurat (2012)[16] present the impact of mobility on a scheme called Location-based Routing with Adaptive Request Zone (LoRAREZ). In LoRAREZ, the size of expected zone and request zone is set adaptively based on distance between the sources node and destination node. Proposed protocol evaluates the impact of mobility on the performance of LoRAREZ regarding packet delivery fraction, routing overhead, end-to-end delay, and throughput and power consumption by comparing with those of the traditional Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) and Modified Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (MAODV).

Haiying Shen et al. (2013)[17] have proposed An Anonymous Location-Based Efficient Routing Protocol [ALERT] for MANETs. The proposed system dynamically divides the network field into zones and arbitrarily selects nodes in zones as intermediate relay nodes, which form a no traceable anonymous route. It also offers anonymity protection to sources, destinations, and routes by hiding the data initiator among many initiators. When compare to GPSR geographical routing protocol ALERT achieves significant routing efficiency

Vijendran, Anna Saro, and J. Viji Gripsy. (2014) [18] proposed Rectangular Zone based Location Specific Routing (RZLSR) approach which is efficient regarding energy, it is more adaptive, secure and uses labels to carry the disjointness-threshold between nodes during the route discovery which improves the quality of services. There is a necessity to develop an energy efficient sensor network for an industrial market, who greatly concern about the energy because these sectors increases the demand for energy. This research study mainly focuses on secure and energy efficient routing in MASNet by adapting the RZLSR. A secure multipath algorithm has been presented in this paper. And this assists the nodes in MASNET to carry out ondemandroute discovery. This also help in forming set of paths while identifying a disjointness threshold. The disjointness threshold is the maximal number of nodes shared between any two paths in the set of the k determined routes. The broadcasting scheme used in this approach is based on RECT. This forms an efficient framework for routing data between source and destination. A set of security mechanisms, based on use of Watchdog and digital signature, are used to protect the route discovery process. The experimental results denote that the RZLSR approach presented significant performance with lesser overhead, energy efficient and better network lifetime.

Vijendran, Anna Saro, and J. Viji Gripsy (2014)[19] proposed a secure multipath algorithm, which facilitates the nodes in MASNet to execute on-demand discovery and forming set of paths. An Enhanced Secure Multipath Routing (ESMR) is formed with an adaptive behavior on route discovery, and route maintenance phase. In this paper, authors

have developed two algorithms named as DMPR and QUAD for route discovery, and route maintenance. This proposal messages are broadcasted only to limit nodes using QUAD scheme which can efficiently reduce the time to establish the path between source and destination nodes. This paper investigates the proposed algorithms with SeMuRAMAS algorithm. To achieve efficient, secure and reliable multi-path routing for MASNETS, propose a routing mechanism which allows nodes in MASNet to perform an ondemand discovery and generation of a set of paths, based on Dynamic MPR (DMPR) protocol for route discovery process A set of security mechanisms, based on the utilization of Watchdog and digital signature, are used to protect the route discovery process. The simulation results indicate that the proposed approach provides significant performance with lesser overhead, energy efficient and better network lifetime.

Jebaseelan, Viji Gripsy, and Anithalakshmi Srinivasan (2017)[20] authors developed a new lightweight route selection scheme named as ArcRect with the security concern over MASNET. In this scheme, the routing attack targets are identified and avoided by deploying intellectual watchdog (IWT) and lightweight key verification mechanisms. The combination of energy effective and secure location aided routing scheme also helps to shrink the search space than the other approaches. This used the curved rectangle zone selection for shrinking route search space. The core functionality of the proposed work regarding cost effective and secure route selection is validated by NS-2 tool.

Karthick, Suyambu (2018) [21] proposed a novel routing protocol is proposed named as Trust Distrust Protocol (TDP). In the TDP protocol initially, the topology management is done by using an improved k-means algorithm. Then the fitness of every node is calculated by sending and receiving a set of sample packets (or hello packet), the ratio of receiving to transmitting is denoted as trust ability or the fitness of a node. This protocol helps to find out the trusted and distrusted node at the time of communication.

3. IMPLEMENTATION OF PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Even though a Mobile Ad hoc sensor networks have many challenges that need to be addressed, the objective of this work is to address the problems in energy consumption minimization in the data dissemination with security considerations using location aided routing and the route consistency in using single and multipath with conservation of energy. In the traditional routing, conventional protocols are used with flooding packets for data dissemination. However, the flooding mechanism suffers from many drawbacks such as data duplication, congestion in case of security violations, etc. another main disadvantage of MASNET is its energy resource availability. Limited battery and energy based resources restrict the new approaches to handle security and path reliability. So, there is a necessity for an energy-efficient routing mechanism for information dissemination in MASNET. An energy-efficient routing mechanism can be achieved by

Location Aided routing (LAR), to improve the results with more effective manner for MASNET has been proposed in this paper, which overcomes the drawbacks in the existing location-based protocols. A new mobility aware dynamic location aided secure routing is proposed with improved energy reduction techniques. Several existing works [18][20] used rectangular zone along with the global information of node location. But, those techniques affected by scalability issues and it needs every node need to be active all time for sharing location information.

TRANSVERSE WAVES RECTANGULAR WITH DYNAMIC ADAPTIVE SECURE ROUTING (TWRDASR):

To achieve high secure energy effective location aided routing, the proposed work introduced a Transverse Wave Rectangular with Dynamic Adaptive Secure Routing (TWRDASR) mechanism. The TWRDASR reduces the number of nodes in the route discovery process, so that it can drastically reduce the flooding to all nodes and consumes less energy. The proposed work can effectively increase the packet delivery ratio, throughput and security in MASNET. The proposed system maintains consistency in path selection, and data dissemination.

In the proposed mobile adhoc sensor network, the node regions are segmented as virtual transverse curved into virtual regions at the time of Route Request (RREQ). In the existing system, the packets distributed overall the nodes which increase high energy consumption. To overcome this problem, in literature Rectangular Zone based Location Specific Routing (RZLSR) approach proposed, here the rectangular zone is created for packet flooding. However, the security features are not considered in this approach. Location-based Routing with Adaptive Request Zone (LoRAReZ) also proposed with adaptive zone selection. After analyzing the drawbacks of existing works, a new approach is proposed. The TWRDASR has been discussed in detail in this section. In the TWRDASR, the region selection is non-uniform and organized as rectangular curve initially, after that, the zone is adjusted transversely.

To communicate with other mobile nodes in the homogeneous network, the dynamic arc initiates its mobile nodes with a set of parameters. After initialization, the nodes in the zone are monitored and the mobility will be predicted. The temporal mobility prediction process helps to know the node movement status and assures for the consistent path selection in the transverse wave in rect arc. The enhanced energy conservation is done by the appropriation of densely populated mobile sensor nodes to the monitoring zone. It avoids redundant communication among neighbors and increases the lifetime of every node in the network. Further, the proposed system measures the network connectivity directly and adaptively by itself. It can find network redundancy and node mobility more accurately. It initiates the on demand mobility analysis and reporting process along with the node authentication in MASNET. The TWRDASR has different phases such as node

initialization, zone selection, location information and mobility analysis, route discovery, node authentication, and data dissemination. The first step in the proposed work uses a request zone that is rectangular shape initially and then the wave rectangular is created. The shape of wave zone is given in Fig. 1. In MASNET, the node initialization begins with the set of parameters such as node id, initial localization, energy and other resources. After successful node initialization, the node starts data dissemination process.

Fig. a. The Transverse Wave Zone Shape

Consider the nodes are initiated in the network, form that node A and Node B has selected as source and destination. Also consider that node A initiate the route discovery to disseminate data to node N. the proposed work gets the RREQ from the node A and finds the location of node B from the node initialization process. Here the node B was at location (X_b, Y_b) at the time t_0 . On time t_1 , node A initiate a new route discovery for destination B. it assumes that node A received the node mobility of node B using its average speed s with which node B can move. Using this, node A defines the expected zone on time t_1 to be the wave rectangle of zone size $Z = s(t_1 - t_0)$ centered at location (X_b, Y_b) . In some cases, the system gets the maximum speed of a need instead of the average speed.

Fig. b. The TWRDASR in the transverse wave zone

In the TWRDASR approach, the request zone is defined to be the nominal Transverse wave rectangle that includes current location of node A and the expected zone, which is represented in the circular region in Fig. 2.0. Here the shape is wave, so it can adapt the network size and minimizes the flooding count. The rectangle wave is like transverse to the x and y axis. In Fig. 2, the request zone is the wave rectangle with transverse whose corners are represented as 1,2,3 and 4. The source node A can, thus, determine the four corners of the request zone, which is in the transverse wave rectangle and the node A includes their coordinates with the route request message transmitted when initiating route discovery begins. In the proposed work the node receives the RREQ message only when the nodes in the wave rectangle. This simply verifies the virtual corner position of 1,2,3 and 4. The zone is dynamically updated by the network process at the time route discovery. Here the red color node comes in the out of boundary, so it eliminates the RREQ.

When node B, ie the destination receives the RREQ, it replies by sending a route reply (RREP) message in the same path. Here node localization process is performed in this phase, which gathers the current location and time along with the node unique id in the RREP. For security reasons, the proposed work utilizes a high secure node id to identify each node in the network. At the end of route discovery process, the node A ie the source node receives the RREP and verifies the RREP sequence by node id and continues data dissemination to node B. for a particular temporal gap, the node A utilizes the node localization information to select the request zone in the future route selection process. This also includes the mobility details, which can determine the time of RREP validity. This helps to reuse the path if the node is very less mobility in the zone.

The TWRDASR utilizes the mobile nodes localization and mobility prediction models. This helps to maintain the network connectivity among all mobile nodes in the MASN. This is done with the help of protocol and that estimates the mobility based on every temporal gap. This helps to declare the mobile nodes which will leave the zone soon. The node leaving time is estimated as M/s where s is the node- current speed and M is its mobility movement range. If the M/s estimate is too large, the connectivity between the moving node and the source node might be lost and the RREQ should be done again. However, if this ratio is too small and the mobility speed is very less in the network, then there is no need to call the route discovery process. So this will decrease the energy consumption at the time of route discovery. In our TWRDASR implementation, we set the estimate as M/Ts to balance the energy conservation and connectivity, where T is a constant determined by the transverse wave arc formation. We extend the basic route discovery message to include the predicted node fading time form the zone.

ALGORITHM -TWRDASR

Step 1: Initialize the N number of nodes in the network zone NZ.

Step 2: Provide a unique id N_i for every node in the network.

Step 3: Segment the mobile region into transverse arced wave rectangle, based on the topography and rectangle size as given below.

- Let R_i represent the radius of the sector to form the transverse arc where 'i' is the ith transverse wave.
- Initially transverse wave are constructed throughout the network by fixing the difference $R_{i+1} - R_i$.
- The threshold value of the number of nodes can be decided based on the topography and the zone size.
- Whenever nodes are densely deployed; and when the number of nodes exceeds the threshold value, 'i' can be incremented and the number of transverse arcs can be increased within the topography to account for a minimal number of nodes with each transverse arc region.

Step 4: For each node in the NZ, based on its location in one of the zones created, set the zone id and maintain the node count in every dynamic zone. If the node count of the zone exceeds the threshold value, Get the dimensions of the zone and the new zone size. Split the zone based on the input parameters. Maintain the count of the number of zones formed. Set a new zone id for the node, based on its location in one of the new zones formed. Identify the neighbors and store in the neighbor list.

Step 5: The source node A creates a RREQ packet with its id, sequence number, node list, zone id, and node type and node list length. The node list contains its id and the ids of all its neighbours

Step 6: The source node broadcasts the RREQ to its neighbors in the specific zone transversely.

Step 7: every neighbor node receives the RREQ and forwards to the next node in the zone.

Step 8: The receiver node receives the RREQ and sends a RREP along with the N_i , node location information L and the mobility info M. RREP(N_i, L, M) along with the temporal gap T.

Step 9: disseminate data packets d to the destination node B.

Step 10: Update the acknowledgement (Ack) for security in the packet header and maintain the log for the temporal gap T.

The proposed system performs a new tagging process at the time of RREP and data dissemination, which includes an acknowledgement about the forwarding node. This includes the node id and the success ratio of the particular node from the last temporal interval transactions. This security procedure doesn't incur more cost, because it utilizes time based node acknowledgement with unique id. The node id generation task is performed in the node initialization process. The algorithm step shows the overall process included in the proposed work.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation of the proposed work has done using NS2 with 50,100 nodes respectively. Different simulation times were used to analyze with different set of nodes. The performance with respect to energy consumption for various location aided routing techniques is analyzed by simulating the network and implementing the protocols in the network simulator tool Ns2.35. the total simulation area used is 20x20 sq. m. The data dissemination occurring over different propagation time for various zone sizes has been obtained. The total data dissemination is also determined for changing pause times from 2 to 40 sec. The energy consumption is also observed over duration of 2 to 40 seconds. A simulation environment is developed and major Quality of Service (QOS) parameters are compared with the existing schemes. The most recent approaches from the literature is considered for the comparison. The major performance parameters such as Energy Consumption and successful data delivery. The performance of various location aided routing techniques was estimated from the same simulation scenario, and a comparative

analysis with ArcRect is performed. The ArcRect algorithm adopts a curved rectangular based zone selection for energy effective data dissemination and hence, effective dissemination of data with reduced energy consumption is achieved. Increasing the number of heterogeneous mobile nodes within a particular zone reduces the number of active nodes at a time. Hence, the energy consumed reduces with a dynamic adaptive zone selection scheme.

COMPARISION TABLE 1

Energy (mj)	ArcRect	TWRect
5	0.83	0.68
10	0.85	0.72
15	1.88	0.99
20	1.89	1.02
25	2.91	1.93
30	2.92	2.23
35	3.93	2.95
40	3.93	3.01
45	4.94	3.97

Fig. c. Energy consumption comparison chart

The simulation is carried out with a network area of 50 nodes having dynamic mobility model. From the obtained simulation results shown in Fig. 3, more data gets disseminated with reduced consumption of energy for a network having different mobility values in various zones that are developed as per the algorithm. From the obtained simulation results, it is evident that consumption of energy gets reduced in the proposed algorithm.

COMPARISION TABLE II

Time	TWRect	ArcRect
100	5	8
200	11	15
300	12	18
400	12	19
500	13	21
600	14	24
700	14	25
800	14	32
900	14	39
1000	14.2	40

Fig. d. Resource Utilization Comparison between Techniques

The Fig. 4 shows the overall resource utilization includes the RREQ message generation, verification and authentication and RREP with acknowledgement. The overall resource

usage is minimized in the proposed system when the maximum transmission speed is 1000mbits/s. The proposed work utilizes the resource in stable. Thus, the overall process in the proposed system is achieved effective resource usage.

A. Overall comparison

The TABLE I shows the overall comparison from the simulation results. This includes the total packets sent and received, dropped packets and the routing overhead. This has been compared with the existing ArcRect approach.

TABLE I. Results from existing and proposed approaches.

Parameters	Techniques	
	ArcRect	TWRDAS R
Total packets	342	342
Received packets	339	240
Dropped packet	5	2
Routing overhead	0.920	0.839

From the analysis and comparison, the proposed system yields much positive results in all parameters like overhead and packet delivery ratio. The comparative study has done with 50 nodes. From the simulation, the results are gathered for the further analysis with different QOS metrics.

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No of pkts send          342
No of pkts recv          339
Pkt delivery ratio       99.1228
Control overhead:        312
Normalized routing overheads 0.920354
Delay:                    0.0786114
Throughput                71425
Jitter                    0.0597241
No of Pkts Dropped       3

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Fig. 5. Results of the ArcRect with 50 nodes

Total Sent Packets	342
Total Received Packets	340
Packet delivery ratio(PDR)	99.8994
Normalized routing overheads	0.83995
Control overhead:	278
Delay:	0.0111322
Throughput	97342
Jitter	0.0582527
Total Dropped Packets	2

Fig. 6 Results of the TWRDASR with 50 nodes

The experiment is carried with 50 nodes with dynamic mobile environment. This experiment produces best result in terms of PDR, energy effective and throughput, because the proposed TWRDASR approach reduces the searching zone in more effective, so the routing overhead is reduced. The results of the existing and proposed approach are specified in the Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 respectively. The packet delivery ratio is 99.8% in the proposed system when there are 50 nodes. This may be varying according to the total number of nodes and its energy.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented a new approach for location aided routing in MASNET with dynamic adaptive features. The proposed work provided a detailed introduction about the MASNET and the existing approaches on location based routing protocols used in mobile ad hoc sensor network. From this paper we conclude that, by using security features and node location information along with the traditional zone shrinking process may improve the performance of the network. This will reduce the energy consumption in MASNET. The maximum approaches have used flooding restriction approaches, which is useful for reducing the search zone in the MASNET route discovery. Using these techniques along with the mobility prediction process, the network and communication overhead can greatly reduced. And this can give high value in packet delivery ratio (PDR). After the detailed analysis and simulation on the location aided routing, a new protocol is deployed with transverse wave rectangular zone. This proposal drastically reduces the resource consumption in an effective manner. In future by using hybrid technique the exchange route and security information from one node to another node can be easier.

Data Availability:

The data used to support the findings of this study are not available to share. The simulation results generated many trace files and from that trace files, the results have generated. In this article, some synthetic data is newly created and used to analyze the effectiveness of this study.

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